

**AN
INTERNSHIP REPORT
ON
ONLINE DISCUSSION PROJECT MANAGEMENT SYSTEM
REPORT
BY
KAMAL ACHARYA
(Tribhuvan University)**

Date: 2025/07/02

Online Discuss-Forum

Abstract

The project titled “**Online Discuss-forum**” is designed using Active Server Pages .NET with Microsoft Visual Studio.Net 2008 as front end and Microsoft SQL Server 2000 as back end which works in .Net framework version 3.5. The coding language used is C# .Net.

This project is aimed at developing online form for the group discussion. This is a web-based tool. Any user can post the doubts topics and can reply for the other user doubts. The user can invites others for Discussion and submit query. This is useful for a small office, school or a department or for that matter any group who is interested to organize it effectively. Facility to share the resource and post articles that can be viewed by registered user.

Functional components of the project

Following is a list of functionality of the system. More functionality that you find appropriate can be added to this list. And, in places where the description of functionality is not adequate, you can make appropriate assumptions and proceed.

Users of the system:

Following are the requirements, which can be used to derive functional components:

1. Users need to register.
2. Facility to post topics for the discussion.
3. Facility to view the articles by topics
4. User can view the previous discussion taken place on that day.
5. Rate the articles .
6. Administrator has privilege to edit user’s profile

TABLE OF CONTENTS

CHAPTER NO	TITLE	PAGE NO
	ABSTRACT	
	LIST OF TABLES	
	LIST OF FIGURES	
	LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS	
1.	INTRODUCTION	
	1.1 ABOUT THE ORGANIZATION	
	1.2 PROJECT DESCRIPTION	
2.	SYSTEM STUDY	
	2.1 FEASABILITY STUDY	
	2.2 EXISTING SYSTEM	
	2.3 PROPOSED SYSTEM	
3	SYSTEM SPECIFICATION	
	3.1 SOFTWARE REQUIREMENTS	
	3.2 HARDWARE REQUIREMENTS	
4	LANGUAGE SPECIFICATION	
	4.1 FEATURES OF ASP .NET	
	4.2 FEATURES OF SQL Server 2000	
5	SYSTEM DESIGN	
	5.1 INPUT DESIGN	

5.2 OUTPUT DESIGN
5.3 DATABASE DESIGN
5.4 DATA FLOW DIAGRAM

6 SYSTEM TESTING AND MAINTENANCE

6.1 UNIT TESTING
6.2 INTEGRATION TESTING
6.3 VALIDATION TESTING
6.4 VERIFICATION TESTING

7 SYSTEM IMPLEMENTATION

7.1 SCOPE FOR FUTURE DEVELOPMENT

8 CONCLUSION

9 BIBLIOGRAPHY

APPENDIX

- SCREEN SHOT
- DATA TABLE STRUCTURE
- SAMPLE CODING

I.

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 ABOUT THE ORGANISATION

COMPANY PROFILE

At APT Technologies, We go beyond providing software solutions. We work with our client's technologies and business changes that shape their competitive advantages.

Founded in 2000, APT Technologies. is a software and service provider that helps organizations deploy, manage, and support their business-critical software more effectively. Utilizing a combination of proprietary software, services and specialized expertise, APT Technologies. helps mid-to-large enterprises, software companies and IT service providers improve consistency, speed, and transparency with service delivery at lower costs. APT Technologies. helps companies avoid many of the delays, costs and risks associated with the distribution and support of software on desktops, servers and remote devices.

Our automated solutions include rapid, touch-free deployments, ongoing software upgrades, fixes and security patches, technology asset inventory and tracking, software license optimization, application self-healing and policy management. At Blue Chip Technologies, we go beyond providing software solutions. We work with our clients' technologies and business processes that shape their competitive advantages.

About The People

As a team we have the prowess to have a clear vision and realize it too. As a statistical evaluation, the team has more than 40,000 hours of expertise in providing real-time solutions in the fields of Embedded Systems, Control systems, Micro-Controllers, c Based Interfacing, Programmable Logic Controller, VLSI Design And Implementation, Networking With C++, java, client Server Technologies in Java,(J2EE\J2ME\J2SE\EJB),VB & VC++, Oracle and operating system concepts with LINUX.

Our Vision

“Dreaming a vision is possible and realizing it is our goal”.

Our Mission

We have achieved this by creating and perfecting processes that are in par with the global standards and we deliver high quality, high value services, reliable and cost effective IT products to clients around the world.

1.2 PROJECT DESCRIPTION

The project titled “**ONLINE DISCUSS FORUM**” is designed using Active Server Pages .NET and SQL Server 2000 which runs under .Net Frame Work 2005 in Microsoft Windows Operating System family.

The project contains seven main modules.

- Category
- Post Question
- Registration
- Answer
- Discover
- Articles
- Search

Category Module:

This module is the main module, by selecting the category user can post their questions easily. They can retrieve the answers for their questions from the different users.

Post Question Module:

This module is mainly for the registered users. As the Administrator has to know who has posted the questions the user is registered here. These registered users alone can post their question in detailed manner.

Registration Module:

This Module helps to give the detailed information about the newly entered user.

Answer Module:

Each and every posted question will get the exact answer from the Discussion Forum team and also they can get a lot of answers from the different user.

Discover Module:

Users can answer the questions which are posted in this site. Both registered and non registered user is benefited over this module. They can also view the answers posted in this site.

Articles Module:

User can post their invention and also they can know about the ideas of the all Users.

Search Module

This module is used to search their queries , the articles and also the inventions. Both registered and non registered users can search over here

2. SYSTEM STUDY

2.1 FEASIBILITY STUDY:

The feasibility of the project is analyzed in this phase and business proposal is put forth with a very general plan for the project and some cost estimates. During system analysis the feasibility study of the proposed system is to be carried out. This is to ensure that the proposed system is not a burden to the company. For feasibility analysis, some understanding of the major requirements for the system is essential.

Three key considerations involved in the feasibility analysis are

- ∞ ECONOMICAL FEASIBILITY
- ∞ TECHNICAL FEASIBILITY
- ∞ SOCIAL FEASIBILITY

ECONOMICAL FEASIBILITY

This study is carried out to check the economic impact that the system will have on the organization. The amount of fund that the company can pour into the research and development of the system is limited. The expenditures must be justified. Thus the developed system as well within the budget and this was achieved because most of the technologies used are freely available. Only the customized products had to be purchased.

TECHNICAL FEASIBILITY

This study is carried out to check the technical feasibility, that is, the technical requirements of the system. Any system developed must not have a high demand on the available technical resources. This will lead to high demands on the available technical resources. This will lead to high demands being placed on the client. The developed system must have a modest requirement, as only minimal or null changes are required for implementing this system.

SOCIAL FEASIBILITY

The aspect of study is to check the level of acceptance of the system by the user. This includes the process of training the user to use the system efficiently. The user must not feel threatened by the system, instead must accept it as a necessity. The level of acceptance by the users solely depends on the methods that are employed to educate the user about the system and to make him familiar with it. His level of confidence must be raised so that he is also able to make some constructive criticism, which is welcomed, as he is the final user of the system.

2.2 EXISTING SYSTEM

In general people share their ideas, queries and answers from their colleagues or friends through the intercom or direct manner. They need to spend time for their work.

DRAWBACKS

Some of the drawbacks are:

1. Details are enquired through phone.
2. It consumes more time
3. They don't get proper answers.

2.3 PROPOSED SYSTEM

It is difficult to note down all the problems manually. Instead it is decided to develop an “**ONLINE DISCUSS FORUM**” to ease the operation.

A system is required which is being capable of elimination all the problems and become useful to users and thus the new system is derived. Here we get a different view from different users.

BENEFITS

1. Interaction will be easier.
2. Users articles can be viewed by others
3. Less time consuming.

3. SYSTEM SPECIFICATION

3.1 HARDWARE REQUIREMNTS

The hardware used for the development of the project is:

PROCESSOR	:	PENTIUM III 866 MHz
RAM	:	128 MD SD RAM
MONITOR	:	15" COLOR
HARD DISK	:	20 GB
FLOPPY DRIVE	:	1.44 MB
CD DRIVE	:	LG 52X
KEYBOARD	:	STANDARD 102 KEYS
MOUSE	:	3 BUTTONS

3.2 SOFTWARE REQUIREMNTS

The software used for the development of the project is:

OPERATING SYSTEM	:	Windows XP Professional
ENVIRONMENT	:	Visual Studio .NET 2003
.NET FRAMEWORK	:	Version 1.1
LANGUAGE	:	C#.NET, ASP.NET
BACKEND	:	SQL SERVER 2000

4. LANGUAGE SPECIFICATION

THE .NET FRAMEWORK

The .NET Framework is a new computing platform that simplifies application development in the highly distributed environment of the Internet.

OBJECTIVES OF .NET FRAMEWORK:

1. To provide a consistent object-oriented programming environment whether object codes is stored and executed locally on Internet-distributed, or executed remotely.
2. To provide a code-execution environment to minimizes software deployment and guarantees safe execution of code.
3. Eliminates the performance problems.

There are different types of application, such as Windows-based applications and Web-based applications.

To make communication on distributed environment to ensure that code be accessed by the .NET Framework can integrate with any other code.

COMPONENTS OF .NET FRAMEWORK

1. THE COMMON LANGUAGE RUNTIME (CLR):

The common language runtime is the foundation of the .NET Framework. It manages code at execution time, providing important services such as memory management, thread management, and remoting and also ensures more security and robustness. The concept of code management is a fundamental principle of the runtime. Code that targets the runtime is known as managed code, while code that does not target the runtime is known as unmanaged code.

THE .NET FRAME WORK CLASS LIBRARY:

It is a comprehensive, object-oriented collection of reusable types used to develop applications ranging from traditional command-line or graphical user interface (GUI) applications to applications based on the latest innovations provided by ASP.NET, such as Web Forms and XML Web services.

The .NET Framework can be hosted by unmanaged components that load the common language runtime into their processes and initiate the execution of managed code, thereby creating a software environment that can exploit both managed and unmanaged features. The .NET Framework not only provides several runtime hosts, but also supports the development of third-party runtime hosts.

Internet Explorer is an example of an unmanaged application that hosts the runtime (in the form of a MIME type extension). Using Internet Explorer to host the runtime to enables embeds managed components or Windows Forms controls in HTML documents.

FEATURES OF THE COMMON LANGUAGE RUNTIME:

The common language runtime manages memory; thread execution, code execution, code safety verification, compilation, and other system services these are all run on CLR.

Security.

Robustness.

Productivity.

Performance.

SECURITY:

The runtime enforces code access security. The security features of the runtime thus enable legitimate Internet-deployed software to be exceptionally feature rich. With regards to security, managed components are awarded varying degrees of trust, depending on a number of factors that include their origin to perform file-access operations, registry-access operations, or other sensitive functions.

ROBUSTNESS:

The runtime also enforces code robustness by implementing a strict type- and code-verification infrastructure called the common type system(CTS). The CTS ensures that all managed code is self-describing. The managed environment of the runtime eliminates many common software issues.

PRODUCTIVITY:

The runtime also accelerates developer productivity. For example, programmers can write applications in their development language of choice, yet take full advantage of the runtime, the class library, and components written in other languages by other developers.

PERFORMANCE:

The runtime is designed to enhance performance. Although the common language runtime provides many standard runtime services, managed code is never interpreted. A feature called just-in-time (JIT) compiling enables all managed code to run in the native machine language of the system on which it is executing. Finally, the runtime can be hosted by high-performance, server-side applications, such as Microsoft® SQL Server™ and Internet Information Services (IIS).

4.1 FEATURES OF ASP.NET

ASP.NET

ASP.NET is the next version of Active Server Pages (ASP); it is a unified Web development platform that provides the services necessary for developers to build enterprise-class Web applications. While ASP.NET is largely syntax compatible, it also provides a new programming model and infrastructure for more secure, scalable, and stable applications.

ASP.NET is a compiled, NET-based environment, we can author applications in any .NET compatible language, including Visual Basic .NET, C#, and JScript .NET. Additionally, the entire .NET Framework is available to any ASP.NET application. Developers can easily access the benefits of these technologies, which include the managed common language runtime environment (CLR), type safety, inheritance, and so on.

ASP.NET has been designed to work seamlessly with WYSIWYG HTML editors and other programming tools, including Microsoft Visual Studio .NET. Not only does this make Web development easier, but it also provides all the benefits that these tools have to offer, including a GUI that developers can use to drop server controls onto a Web page and fully integrated debugging support.

Developers can choose from the following two features when creating an ASP.NET application. Web Forms and Web services, or combine these in any way they see fit. Each is supported by the same infrastructure that allows you to use authentication schemes, cache frequently used data, or customize your application's configuration, to name only a few possibilities. Web Forms allows us to build powerful forms-based Web pages. When building these pages, we can use ASP.NET server controls to create common UI elements, and program them for common tasks. These controls allow us to rapidly build a Web Form out of reusable built-in or custom components, simplifying the code of a page.

An XML Web service provides the means to access server functionality remotely. Using Web services, businesses can expose programmatic interfaces to their data or business logic, which in turn can be obtained and manipulated by client and server applications. XML Web services enable the exchange of data in client-server or server-server scenarios, using standards like HTTP and XML messaging to move data across firewalls. XML Web services are not tied to a particular component technology or object-calling convention. As a result, programs written in any language, using any component model, and running on any operating system can access XML Web services

Each of these models can take full advantage of all ASP.NET features, as well as the power of the .NET Framework and .NET Framework common language runtime. Accessing databases from ASP.NET applications is an often-used technique for displaying data to Web site visitors. ASP.NET makes it easier than ever to access databases for this purpose. It also allows us to manage the database from your code .

ASP.NET provides a simple model that enables Web developers to write logic that runs at the application level. Developers can write this code in the `global.aspx` text file or in a compiled class deployed as an assembly. This logic can include application-level events, but developers can easily extend this model to suit the needs of their Web application.

ASP.NET provides easy-to-use application and session-state facilities that are familiar to ASP developers and are readily compatible with all other .NET Framework APIs. ASP.NET offers the `IHttpHandler` and `IHttpModule` interfaces. Implementing the `IHttpHandler` interface gives you a means of interacting with the low-level request and response services of the IIS Web server and provides functionality much like ISAPI extensions, but with a simpler programming model. Implementing the `IHttpModule` interface allows you to include custom events that participate in every request made to your application.

ASP.NET takes advantage of performance enhancements found in the .NET Framework and common language runtime. Additionally, it has been designed to offer significant performance improvements over ASP and other Web development platforms. All ASP.NET code is compiled, rather than interpreted, which allows early binding, strong typing, and just-in-time (JIT) compilation to native code, to name only a few of its benefits. ASP.NET is also easily factorable, meaning that developers can remove modules (a session module, for instance) that are not relevant to the application they are developing.

ASP.NET provides extensive caching services (both built-in services and caching APIs). ASP.NET also ships with performance counters that developers and system administrators can monitor to test new applications and gather metrics on existing applications. Writing custom debug statements to your Web page can help immensely in troubleshooting your application's code. However, it can cause embarrassment if it is not

removed. The problem is that removing the debug statements from your pages when your application is ready to be ported to a production server can require significant effort.

ASP.NET offers the Trace Context class, which allows us to write custom debug statements to our pages as we develop them. They appear only when you have enabled tracing for a page or entire application. Enabling tracing also appends details about a request to the page, or, if you so specify, to a custom trace viewer that is stored in the root directory of your application. The .NET Framework and ASP.NET provide default authorization and authentication schemes for Web applications. we can easily remove, add to, or replace these schemes, depending upon the needs of our application .

ASP.NET configuration settings are stored in XML-based files, which are human readable and writable. Each of our applications can have a distinct configuration file and we can extend the configuration scheme to suit our requirements.

DATA ACCESS WITH ADO.NET

As you develop applications using ADO.NET, you will have different requirements for working with data. You might never need to directly edit an XML file containing data - but it is very useful to understand the data architecture in ADO.NET.

ADO.NET offers several advantages over previous versions of ADO:

- Interoperability
- Maintainability
- Programmability
- Performance Scalability

INTEROPERABILITY:

ADO.NET applications can take advantage of the flexibility and broad acceptance of XML. Because XML is the format for transmitting datasets across the network, any component that can read the XML format can process data. The receiving component need not be an ADO.NET component.

The transmitting component can simply transmit the dataset to its destination without regard to how the receiving component is implemented. The destination component might be a Visual Studio application or any other application implemented with any tool whatsoever.

The only requirement is that the receiving component be able to read XML. SO, XML was designed with exactly this kind of interoperability in mind.

MAINTAINABILITY:

In the life of a deployed system, modest changes are possible, but substantial, Architectural changes are rarely attempted because they are so difficult. As the performance load on a deployed application server grows, system resources can become scarce and response time or throughput can suffer. Faced with this problem, software architects can choose to divide the server's business-logic processing and user-interface processing onto separate tiers on separate machines.

In effect, the application server tier is replaced with two tiers, alleviating the shortage of system resources. If the original application is implemented in ADO.NET using datasets, this transformation is made easier.

ADO.NET data components in Visual Studio encapsulate data access functionality in various ways that help you program more quickly and with fewer mistakes.

PERFORMANCE:

ADO.NET datasets offer performance advantages over ADO disconnected record sets. In ADO.NET data-type conversion is not necessary.

SCALABILITY:

ADO.NET accommodates scalability by encouraging programmers to conserve limited resources. Any ADO.NET application employs disconnected access to data; it does not retain database locks or active database connections for long durations.

VISUAL STUDIO .NET

Visual Studio .NET is a complete set of development tools for building ASP Web applications, XML Web services, desktop applications, and mobile applications. In addition to building high-performing desktop applications, you can use Visual Studio's powerful component-based development tools and other technologies to simplify team-based design, development, and deployment of Enterprise solutions.

Visual Basic .NET, Visual C++ .NET, and Visual C# .NET all use the same integrated development environment (IDE), which allows them to share tools and facilitates in the creation of mixed-language solutions.

In addition, these languages leverage the functionality of the .NET Framework and simplify the development of ASP Web applications and XML Web services.

Visual Studio supports the .NET Framework, which provides a common language runtime and unified programming classes; ASP.NET uses these components to create ASP Web applications and XML Web services. Also it includes MSDN Library, which contains all the documentation for these development tools.

4.2 FEATURES OF SQL-SERVER 2000

The OLAP Services feature available in SQL Server version 7.0 is now called SQL Server 2000 Analysis Services. The term OLAP Services has been replaced with the term Analysis Services. Analysis Services also includes a new data mining component. The Repository component available in SQL Server version 7.0 is now called Microsoft SQL Server 2000 Meta Data Services. References to the component now use the term Meta Data Services. The term repository is used only in reference to the repository engine within Meta Data Services

SQL-SERVER database consist of six type of objects,

They are,

1. TABLE
2. QUERY
3. FORM
4. REPORT
5. MACRO

TABLE:

A database is a collection of data about a specific topic.

VIEWS OF TABLE:

We can work with a table in two types,

1. Design View
2. Datasheet View

Design View

To build or modify the structure of a table we work in the table design view.

We can specify what kind of data will be hold.

Datasheet View

To add, edit or analyses the data itself we work in tables datasheet view mode.

QUERY:

A query is a question that has to be asked the data. Access gathers data that answers the question from one or more table. The data that make up the answer is either dynaset (if you edit it) or a snapshot(it cannot be edited).Each time we run query, we get latest information in the dynaset.Access either displays the dynaset or snapshot for us to view or perform an action on it ,such as deleting or updating.

FORMS:

A form is used to view and edit information in the database record by record .A form displays only the information we want to see in the way we want to see it. Forms use the familiar controls such as textboxes and checkboxes. This makes viewing and entering data easy.

Views of Form:

We can work with forms in several primarily there are two views,
They are,

1. Design View

2. Form View

Design View

To build or modify the structure of a form, we work in forms design view. We can add control to the form that are bound to fields in a table or query, includes textboxes, option buttons, graphs and pictures.

Form View

The form view which display the whole design of the form.

REPORT:

A report is used to view and print information from the database. The report can group records into many levels and compute totals and average by checking values from many records at once. Also the report is attractive and distinctive because we have control over the size and appearance of it.

MACRO:

A macro is a set of actions. Each action in macros does something. Such as opening a form or printing a report. We write macros to automate the common tasks the work easy and save the time.

MODULE:

Modules are units of code written in access basic language. We can write and use module to automate and customize the database in very sophisticated ways.

It is a personal computer based RDBMS. This provides most of the features available in the high-end RDBMS products like Oracle, Sybase, and Ingress etc. VB keeps access as its native database. Developer can create a database for development & further can create.

The tables are required to store data. During the initial Development phase data can be stored in the access database & during the implementation phase depending on the volume data can use a higher – end database.

5. SYSTEM DESIGN

Design is multi-step process that focuses on data structure software architecture, procedural details, (algorithms etc.) and interface between modules. The design process also translates the requirements into the presentation of software that can be accessed for quality before coding begins.

Computer software design changes continuously as new methods; better analysis and broader understanding evolved. Software Design is at relatively early stage in its revolution.

Therefore, Software Design methodology lacks the depth, flexibility and quantitative nature that are normally associated with more classical engineering disciplines. However techniques for software designs do exist, criteria for design qualities are available and design notation can be applied.

5.1 INPUT DESIGN

Input design is the process of converting user-originated inputs to a computer-based format. Input design is one of the most expensive phases of the operation of computerized system and is often the major problem of a system.

In the project, the input design is made in various web forms with various methods.

For example, in the Admin form, the empty username and password is not allowed. The username if exists in the database, the input is considered to be invalid and is not accepted.

5.2 OUTPUT DESIGN

Output design generally refers to the results and information that are generated by the system for many end-users; output is the main reason for developing the system and the basis on which they evaluate the usefulness of the application.

In the project, once question are posted, It stores in to the data base. The questions are viewed and also the user who needs the details about the question can register and see the related answer which is to be posted this site.

5.3 DATABASE DESIGN

The database design is a must for any application developed especially more for the data store projects. Since the chatting method involves storing the message in the table and produced to the sender and receiver, proper handling of the table is a must.

In the project, login table is designed to be unique in accepting the username and the length of the username and password should be greater than zero.

The complete listing of the tables and their fields are provided in the annexure under the title 'Table Structure'.

5.4 DATA FLOW DIAGRAM

Category Module

Post Question

Answer

Keyword

Article

Level_1

Admin

Question

Answer

ER DIAGRAM

6. SYSTEM TESTING AND MAINTENANCE

6.1 UNIT TESTING

The procedure level testing is made first. By giving improper inputs, the errors occurred are noted and eliminated. Then the web form level testing is made. For example storage of data to the table in the correct manner.

The dates are entered in wrong manner and checked. Wrong email-id and web site URL (Universal Resource Locator) is given and checked.

6.2 INTEGRATION TESTING

Testing is done for each module. After testing all the modules, the modules are integrated and testing of the final system is done with the test data, specially designed to show that the system will operate successfully in all its aspects conditions. Thus the system testing is a confirmation that all is correct and an opportunity to show the user that the system works.

6.3 VALIDATION TESTING

The final step involves Validation testing, which determines whether the software function as the user expected. The end-user rather than the system developer conduct this test most software developers as a process called “Alpha and Beta Testing” to uncover that only the end user seems able to find.

The compilation of the entire project is based on the full satisfaction of the end users. In the project, validation testing is made in various forms. In registration form Email id, phone number and also mandatory fields for the user is verified.

6.4 VERIFICATION TESTING

Verification is a fundamental concept in software design. This is the bridge between customer requirements and an implementation that satisfies those requirements. This is verifiable if it can be demonstrated that the testing will result in an implementation that satisfies the customer requirements.

Inadequate testing or non-testing leads to errors that may appear few months later. This will create two problems

- ✓ Time delay between the cause and appearance of the problem.
- ✓ The effect of the system errors on files and records within the system.

MAINTENANCE

The objectives of this maintenance work are to make sure that the system gets into work all time without any bug. Provision must be for environmental changes which may affect the computer or software system. This is called the maintenance of the system. Nowadays there is the rapid change in the software world. Due to this rapid change, the system should be capable of adapting these changes. In our project the process can be added without affecting other parts of the system.

Maintenance plays a vital role. The system liable to accept any modification after its implementation. This system has been designed to favor all new changes. Doing this will not affect the system's performance or its accuracy.

7. SYSTEM IMPLEMENTATION

Implementation is the most crucial stage in achieving a successful system and giving the user's confidence that the new system is workable and effective. Implementation of a modified application to replace an existing one. This type of conversation is relatively easy to handle, provide there are no major changes in the system.

Each program is tested individually at the time of development using the data and has verified that this program linked together in the way specified in the programs specification, the computer system and its environment is tested to the satisfaction of the user. The system that has been developed is accepted and proved to be satisfactory for the user. And so the system is going to be implemented very soon. A simple operating procedure is included so that the user can understand the different functions clearly and quickly.

Initially as a first step the executable form of the application is to be created and loaded in the common server machine which is accessible to all the user and the server is to be connected to a network. The final stage is to document the entire system which provides components and the operating procedures of the system.

7.1 SCOPE FOR FUTURE DEVELOPMENT

Every application has its own merits and demerits. The project has covered almost all the requirements. Further requirements and improvements can easily be done since the coding is mainly structured or modular in nature. Changing the existing modules or adding new modules can append improvements. Further enhancements can be made to the application, so that the web site functions very attractive and useful manner than the present one.

8. CONCLUSION

It is concluded that the application works well and satisfy the both registered and registered. The application is tested very well and errors are properly debugged. The site is simultaneously accessed from more than one system.

The site works according to the restrictions provided in their respective browsers. The speed of the transactions become more enough now. In this site the user can search the appropriate answers for their questions.. They can view their favorable questions, articles and inventions.

9. BIBLIOGRAPHY

1. STEVE HARRIS AND ROB MACDONALD,
“WEB DEVELOPMENT WITH VB.NET”

-APRES

2. MATTHEW MACDONALD ,
“MICROSOFT VISUAL BASIC.NET PROGRAMMER’S COOKBOOK”

-TATA MCGRAW HILL EDITION

3. CHRIS GOODE, JOHN KAUFFMAN
“BEGINNING ASP.NET 1.0 WITH VISUAL BASIC.NET”

-WROX PROGRAMMER TO PROGRAMMER

4. Douglas O.Reilly ,
“DESIGNING MICROSOFT ASP.NET APPLICATIONS”

-TATA MCGRAW HILL EDITION

Appendix:

SCREEN SHOTS

WebForm1 - Microsoft Internet Explorer

File Edit View Favorites Tools Help

Back Search Favorites

Address http://localhost/ODF_Old_17.08.07/NewUser/NewUserReg.aspx

Discussion Forum

Post Questions View answers Discover

Highland Energy Forum

[Home](#) [Login](#)

[Home](#) » [Register](#)

Register Now! Some of the benefits for registered users:

- ❖ You can submit sample code.
- ❖ Employers and recruiters search for IT talents in member profile page.
- ❖ Receive special gifts for active participation like replying to other user's questions, writing articles etc.
- ❖ Faster response to your queries to our team.

Register

User Name*

Done Local intranet

WebForm1 - Microsoft Internet Explorer

File Edit View Favorites Tools Help

Back Search Favorites

Address http://localhost/ODF_Old_17.08.07/NewUser/NewUserReg.aspx

Full Name* Sunitha

PetName Cheenu

E-Mail* Sunitha@gmail.com

Company/College(Optional) iwiz

Home Page iwiz

Select Ur Question Who is Your Role Model

Give your Answer My Mom

Country india

Detailed Profile : (Optional). Use this space to provide any information about you. Please do not post your resume here.
Please limit the length to less than 25 lines.
You may use HTML tags for formatting. Do not use tags like TITLE, HEAD, TABLE, BODY etc (if you use those tags, we will delete your profile).

Cute site

Submit Cancel

Developed by I WIZ HITEC Solutions

Done Local intranet

UserRegistrationForm2 - Microsoft Internet Explorer

File Edit View Favorites Tools Help

Back Search Favorites

Address http://localhost/ODF_Old_17.08.07/NewUser/MyAccount.aspx

Discussion Forum

Post Questions View answers Discover

Highland Energy Forum

[Home](#) [Login](#)

Registration Made Successfully...

Welcome **Sunitha**

You can Edit all your submissions from this page:

- [Sign Out](#) - Logout from yk5forum.com
- [View My Profile](#)
- [Edit My Personal Information](#) - Edit Name & Address etc.
- [Change Password](#) - Change your current password
- [Upload Photo](#) - Upload a small photo to attach with your profile
- [View Your Questions](#) - View Posted Your Questions And Answers

Done Local intranet

WebForm1 - Microsoft Internet Explorer

File Edit View Favorites Tools Help

Back Search Favorites

Address http://localhost/ODF_Old_17.08.07/NewUser/NewUserReg.aspx

Discussion Forum

Post Questions View answers Discover

Highland Energy Forum

[Home](#) [Login](#)

[Home](#) » [Register](#)

Register Now! Some of the benefits for registered users:

- ❖ You can submit sample code.
- ❖ Employers and recruiters search for IT talents in member profile page.
- ❖ Receive special gifts for active participation like replying to other user's questions, writing articles etc.
- ❖ Faster response to your queries to our team.

Register

User Name*

Done Local intranet

WebForm1 - Microsoft Internet Explorer

File Edit View Favorites Tools Help

Back Search Favorites

Address http://localhost/ODF_Old_17.08.07/NewUser/NewUserReg.aspx

Full Name* Ganesh

PetName Gee

E-Mail* Ganesh@gmail.com

Company/College(Optional) iwiz

Home Page iwiz

Select Ur Question What is Your PetName

Give your Answer Gee

Country india

Detailed Profile : (Optional). Use this space to provide any information about you. Please do not post your resume here.
Please limit the length to less than 25 lines.
You may use HTML tags for formatting. Do not use tags like TITLE, HEAD, TABLE, BODY etc (if you use those tags, we will delete your profile).

Best

Submit Cancel

Developed by I WIZ HITEC Solutions

Done Local intranet

Microsoft Internet Explorer window titled "EditProfile". The address bar shows the URL: `http://localhost/ODF_Old_17.08.07/NewUser/EditProfile.aspx`.

The page header includes navigation links: [Post Questions](#), [View answers](#), and [Discover](#). There is also a logo for "Highland Energy Forum" and links for [Home](#) and [Login](#).

Edit Profile

User Name *	<input type="text" value="Ganeshh"/>
Full Name*	<input type="text" value="Ganesh"/>
PetName	<input type="text" value="Gee"/>
E-Mail*	<input type="text" value="Ganesh@gmail.com"/>
Company/College(Optional)	<input type="text" value="iwiz"/>
Home Page	<input type="text" value="iwiz"/>
Select Ur Question	<input type="text" value="What is Your PetName"/>
Give your Answer	<input type="text" value="Gee"/>
Country	<input type="text" value="india"/>

Detailed Profile : (Optional). Use this space to provide any information about you. Please do not post your resume here.
Please limit the length to less than 25 lines.
You may use HTML tags for formatting. Do not use tags like TITLE, HEAD, TABLE, BODY etc (If you use those tags, we will delete your profile).

Done Local intranet

ChangePassword - Microsoft Internet Explorer

File Edit View Favorites Tools Help

Back Search Favorites

Address http://localhost/ODF_Old_17.08.07/NewUser/ChangePassword.aspx

Discussion Forum

Post Questions View answers Discover

Highland Energy Forum

[Home](#) [Login](#)

User Name* Ganeshh

Current Password *****

New Password* *****

Re-type New Password* *****

Change Button

Developed by I WIZ HITEC Solutions

Done Local intranet

ChangePassword - Microsoft Internet Explorer

File Edit View Favorites Tools Help

Back Search Favorites Home H Links

My Web Search Search Address http://localhost/ODF_Old_17.08.07/NewUser/ChangePassword.aspx Go Links

Discussion Forum

Post Questions View answers Discover

Highland Energy Forum

[Home](#) [Login](#)

User Name* Ganeshh

Current Password

New Password*

Re-type New Password*

Change Button

Your Password Changed Successfully!

Developed by I WIZ HITEC Solutions

Done Local intranet

AskQuestions - Microsoft Internet Explorer

File Edit View Favorites Tools Help

Back Search Favorites

Address http://localhost/ODF_Old_17.08.07/PostQuestions/AskQuestions.aspx

Discussion Forum

Post Questions View answers Discover

Highland Energy Forum

[Home](#) [Login](#)

Ask a Question to Our Team

Your question may be answered by one of our technical team members or other technical visitors of our site.

Categories

- [General](#)
- [Computers](#)
- [Beauty](#)
- [BabyCare](#)
- [Medicine](#)
- [Astrology](#)
- [Sports](#)
- [Buisness](#)

Category

Question Title

Give a meaningful title related to the question, instead of titles like "Please help me", "Any one know the answer etc"

Subject

Question Description

Provide details like which version of the software you

Done Local intranet

UserView - Microsoft Internet Explorer

File Edit View Favorites Tools Help

Back Search Favorites

Address http://localhost/ODF_Old_17.08.07/PostQuestions/UserView.aspx

Discussion Forum

Post Questions View answers Discover

Highland Energy Forum

[Home](#) [Login](#)

Your Open Question

[Edit Your Question](#) [Continue](#)

Tips for Precautions

Developed by I WIZ HITEC Solutions

Done Local intranet

WebForm1 - Microsoft Internet Explorer

File Edit View Favorites Tools Help

Back Forward Stop Refresh Home Search Favorites

My Web Search Search Address http://localhost/ODF_Old_17.08.07/ViewQA/frmQuestion.aspx Go Links

Discussion Forum

Post Questions

View answers

Discover

Highland Energy Forum

[Home](#) [Login](#)

Categories ^

- [General](#)
- [Computers](#)
- [Beauty](#)
- [BabyCare](#)
- [Medicine](#)
- [Astrology](#)
- [Sports](#)
- [Business](#)

Developed by I WIZ HITEC Solutions

http://localhost/ODF_Old_17.08.07/ViewQA/frmQuestion.aspx Local intranet

DATA TABLE STRUCTURE

ARTICLE

	Column Name	Data Type	Length	Allow Nulls
▶ 🔑	ArticleId	int	4	
	CategoryId	int	4	✓
	ArticleSubject	varchar	100	✓
	ArticleLink	varchar	200	✓
	ArticleContent	varchar	100	✓
	KeyId	int	4	✓

CATEGORY

	Column Name	Data Type	Length	Allow Nulls
▶ 🔑	CategoryId	int	4	
	CategoryName	varchar	1000	✓

KEYWORD

	Column Name	Data Type	Length	Allow Nulls
▶ 🔑	KeyId	int	4	
🔑	KeyWord	varchar	100	

QA

	Column Name	Data Type	Length	Allow Nulls
▶ ?	QA Id	int	4	
	UserName	varchar	50	
	QuestionId	int	4	✓
	ADate	varchar	50	
	Answers	varchar	1000	✓
	UserImage	varchar	100	

QUESTION

	Column Name	Data Type	Length	Allow Nulls
▶ ?	QuestionId	int	4	
	Username	varchar	50	✓
	CategoryId	int	4	✓
	KeyId	int	4	✓
	Qdate	smalldatetime	4	✓
	Questions	varchar	1000	✓
	QuestionDescription	varchar	1000	✓

USERS

	Column Name	Data Type	Length	Allow Nulls
▶ ?	UserName	varchar	30	
	UserPassword	varchar	10	✓
	Fullname	varchar	50	✓
	PetName	varchar	50	✓
	Email	varchar	50	✓
	CompanyName	varchar	50	✓
	HomePage	varchar	50	✓
	Country	varchar	50	✓
	DetailProfile	varchar	1000	✓
	SecurityQuestion	varchar	50	✓
	SecurityAnswer	varchar	50	✓
	AccessDare	varchar	50	✓
	UserImage	varchar	100	✓

SAMPLE CODING

Homepage.aspx

```
namespace YK5_Forum.Home
{
    /// <summary>
    /// Summary description for Home.
    /// </summary>
    public class Home : System.Web.UI.Page
    {
        protected System.Web.UI.WebControls.LinkButton lnkUpload;
        protected System.Web.UI.WebControls.LinkButton lnkDownload;

        private void Page_Load(object sender, System.EventArgs e)
        {
            string UserName=Convert.ToString
(Session["UserName"]);
            Session["UserName"]=UserName;

        }

        #region Web Form Designer generated code
        override protected void OnInit(EventArgs e)
        {
            //
            // CODEGEN: This call is required by the ASP.NET Web
Form Designer.
            //
            InitializeComponent();
            base.OnInit(e);
        }

        /// <summary>
        /// Required method for Designer support - do not modify
        /// the contents of this method with the code editor.
        /// </summary>
        private void InitializeComponent()
        {
            this.lnkUpload.Click += new
System.EventHandler(this.LinkButton1_Click);
            this.lnkDownload.Click += new
System.EventHandler(this.lnkDownload_Click);
            this.Load += new System.EventHandler(this.Page_Load);

        }
        #endregion

        private void lnkDownload_Click(object sender,
System.EventArgs e)
        {
```

```

        Response.Redirect("../Articles/DownLoadArticle.aspx");
    }

    private void LinkButton1_Click(object sender,
System.EventArgs e)
    {
        Response.Redirect("../Articles/UploadArticle.aspx");
    }
}
}
}

```

Download Article.aspx

```

namespace YK5_Forum.Answers.Articles
{
    /// <summary>
    /// Summary description for DownLoadArticle.
    /// </summary>
    public class DownLoadArticle : System.Web.UI.Page
    {
        private void Page_Load(object sender, System.EventArgs e)
        {
            // Put user code to initialize the page here
        }

        #region Web Form Designer generated code
        override protected void OnInit(EventArgs e)
        {
            //
            // CODEGEN: This call is required by the ASP.NET Web
Form Designer.
            //
            InitializeComponent();
            base.OnInit(e);
        }

        /// <summary>
        /// Required method for Designer support - do not modify
        /// the contents of this method with the code editor.
        /// </summary>
        private void InitializeComponent()
        {
            this.Load += new System.EventHandler(this.Page_Load);
        }
        #endregion
    }
}

```

```
}
```

User Login.aspx

```
public class UserLogin : System.Web.UI.Page
{
    protected System.Web.UI.WebControls.TextBox TextBox1;
    protected System.Web.UI.WebControls.TextBox TextBox2;
    protected System.Web.UI.WebControls.Button Button1;
    protected System.Web.UI.WebControls.HyperLink HyperLink1;
    protected System.Web.UI.WebControls.HyperLink HyperLink2;
    protected System.Web.UI.WebControls.Label Label1;
    protected System.Web.UI.WebControls.Label Label2;

    general g = new general();

    private void Page_Load(object sender, System.EventArgs e)
    {
        Session["UserName"]=TextBox1.Text;
    }

    #region Web Form Designer generated code
    override protected void OnInit(EventArgs e)
    {
        //
        // CODEGEN: This call is required by the ASP.NET Web
Form Designer.
        //
        InitializeComponent();
        base.OnInit(e);
    }

    /// <summary>
    /// Required method for Designer support - do not modify
    /// the contents of this method with the code editor.
    /// </summary>
    private void InitializeComponent()
    {
        this.Button1.Click += new
System.EventHandler(this.Button1_Click);
        this.Load += new System.EventHandler(this.Page_Load);
    }
    #endregion

    private void Button1_Click(object sender, System.EventArgs
e)
    {
```



```

    }

    #region Web Form Designer generated code
    override protected void OnInit(EventArgs e)
    {
        //
        // CODEGEN: This call is required by the ASP.NET Web
Form Designer.
        //
        InitializeComponent();
        base.OnInit(e);
    }

    /// <summary>
    /// Required method for Designer support - do not modify
    /// the contents of this method with the code editor.
    /// </summary>
    private void InitializeComponent()
    {
        this.Button2.Click += new
System.EventHandler(this.Button2_Click);
        this.Load += new System.EventHandler(this.Page_Load);
    }
    #endregion

    private void Button2_Click(object sender, System.EventArgs
e)
    {
        string image="Null";
        string
AccessDare=Convert.ToString(DateTime.Now.ToShortDateString());
        g.insert("insert into users values('"+
txtusername.Text + "','"+ txtpwd.Text + "','"+ txtfullname.Text
+ "','"+txtPetName.Text+ "','"+ txtemail.Text + "','"+ txtcompany.Text
+ "','"+ txthomepage.Text + "','"+ drcountry.SelectedItem.Text + "','"+
txtdetailedprofile.Text
+ "','"+ drQuestions.SelectedItem.Text+ "','"+txtSecurityAnswer.Text+ "','"+
+AccessDare+ "','"+ image + "')");
        Session["username"]=txtusername.Text;
        Response.Redirect("MyAccount.aspx");
    }

    private void Button4_Click(object sender, System.EventArgs
e)
    {
    }
}
}

```

Edit profile.aspx

```
public SqlConnection con = new
SqlConnection("server=.;database=YK5_Forum;uid=sa;");

private void Page_Load(object sender, System.EventArgs e)
{
    string un=Convert.ToString(Session["UserName"]);
    if (!Page.IsPostBack)
    {
        drQuestions.Items.Add("Select");
        drQuestions.Items.Add("What is Your PetName");
        drQuestions.Items.Add("Who is Your First Class
Teacher");
        drQuestions.Items.Add("Who is Your Role
Model");
        drQuestions.Items.Add("What is your Favorite
dish");
        drQuestions.Items.Add("What is your Favorite
color");
        con.Open();
        SqlCommand cmd = new SqlCommand("select * from
users where username='"+un+"' ", con);
        SqlDataReader dr;
        dr=cmd.ExecuteReader();
        if(dr.Read())
        {
            txtusername.Text=dr[0].ToString();
            txtfullname.Text=dr[2].ToString();
            txtPetName.Text=dr[3].ToString();
            txtemail.Text=dr[4].ToString();
            txtcompany.Text=dr[5].ToString();
            txthomepage.Text=dr[6].ToString();

            drcountry.SelectedItem.Text=dr[7].ToString();

            drQuestions.SelectedItem.Text=dr[9].ToString();
            txtSecurityAnswer.Text=dr[10].ToString();
        }
        con.Close();
    }
}

#region Web Form Designer generated code
override protected void OnInit(EventArgs e)
{
    //
    // CODEGEN: This call is required by the ASP.NET Web
Form Designer.
    //
    InitializeComponent();
}
```

```

        base.OnInit(e);
    }

    /// <summary>
    /// Required method for Designer support - do not modify
    /// the contents of this method with the code editor.
    /// </summary>
    private void InitializeComponent()
    {
        this.Button2.Click += new
System.EventHandler(this.Button2_Click);
        this.Button3.Click += new
System.EventHandler(this.Button3_Click);
        this.Load += new System.EventHandler(this.Page_Load);
    }
    #endregion

    private void Button2_Click(object sender, System.EventArgs
e)
    {
        string un=Convert.ToString(Session["username"]);
        g.insert("update users set UserName='"+
txtusername.Text +"',Fullname='"+ txtfullname.Text +"',PetName='"+
txtPetName.Text +"',Email='"+ txtemail.Text +"',CompanyName='"+
txtcompany.Text +"',HomePage='"+ txthomepage.Text +"',Country='"+
drcountry.SelectedItem.Text +"',securityquestion='"+
drQuestions.SelectedItem.Text +"',securityanswer='"+
txtSecurityAnswer.Text +"' where UserName='"+ un +'");
        Label2.Text="Profile Updated";
        Label2.Visible=true;
        txtusername.Text="";
        txtfullname.Text="";
        txtPetName.Text="";
        txtemail.Text="";
        txtcompany.Text="";
        txthomepage.Text="";
        drcountry.SelectedItem.Text="";
        drQuestions.SelectedItem.Text="";
        txtSecurityAnswer.Text="";
        Session["username"]=un;
    }

    private void Button3_Click(object sender, System.EventArgs
e)
    {
        Response.Redirect("EditProfile.aspx");
    }
}

```

Post question.aspx

```
public class AskQuestions : System.Web.UI.Page
{
    protected System.Web.UI.WebControls.Image Image1;
    protected System.Web.UI.WebControls.Label lblCategoryId;
    protected System.Web.UI.WebControls.TextBox txt_Q_Title;
    protected System.Web.UI.WebControls.TextBox txt_Q_Subject;
    protected System.Web.UI.WebControls.TextBox
txt_Q_Description;
    protected System.Web.UI.WebControls.Button btnSubmit;
    general g=new general();
    private void Page_Load(object sender, System.EventArgs e)
    {
        string id;
        id=Request.QueryString["id"];
        lblCategoryId.Text=id;
        if(!Page.IsPostBack)
        {
            string
UserName=Convert.ToString(Session["UserName"]);
            if(g.scalar("select count(UserName) from Users
where UserName='"+UserName+"'"))
            {
            }
            else
            {
                Response.Redirect("../NewUser/UserLogin.aspx");
            }
            Session["UserName"]=UserName;
        }
    }

    #region Web Form Designer generated code
    override protected void OnInit(EventArgs e)
    {
        //
        // CODEGEN: This call is required by the ASP.NET Web
Form Designer.
        //
        InitializeComponent();
        base.OnInit(e);
    }

    /// <summary>
```

```

        /// Required method for Designer support - do not modify
        /// the contents of this method with the code editor.
        /// </summary>
        private void InitializeComponent()
        {
            this.btnSubmit.Click += new
System.EventHandler(this.btnSubmit_Click);
            this.Load += new System.EventHandler(this.Page_Load);

        }
        #endregion

        private void LinkButton2_Click(object sender,
System.EventArgs e)
        {

        }

        private void btnSubmit_Click(object sender,
System.EventArgs e)
        {
            string
UserName=Convert.ToString(Session["UserName"]);
            string Qdate;
            int Category;
            Category=Convert.ToInt32(Request.QueryString["id"]);

            Qdate=Convert.ToString(DateTime.Now.ToShortDateString());
            g.insert("insert into KeyWord
values('"+txt_Q_Subject.Text+"'");
            string Key=g.ReturnString("select KeyId from Keyword
where Keyword='"+txt_Q_Subject.Text+"'");
            g.insert("insert into Question
values('"+UserName+"','"+Category+"','"+Key+"','"+Qdate+"','"+txt_Q_Title
.Text+"','"+txt_Q_Description.Text+"'");

            Response.Redirect("../PostQuestions/UserView.aspx");
        }

        private void LinkButton1_Click(object sender,
System.EventArgs e)
        {

        }

        private void Button1_Click(object sender, System.EventArgs
e)
        {

        }
    }
}

```

Search .aspx.

```
private void LinkButton1_Click(object sender, System.EventArgs e)
{
    txtarticle.Visible=true;
    btarticle.Visible=true;
    txtqa.Visible=false;
    btqa.Visible=false;
}

private void LinkButton2_Click(object sender,
System.EventArgs e)
{
    txtarticle.Visible=false;
    btarticle.Visible=false;
    txtqa.Visible=true;
    btqa.Visible=true;
}

private void btarticle_Click(object sender,
System.EventArgs e)
{
    string sql="select keyid from keyword WHERE KeyWord
like '%" +txtarticle.Text+"%'";
    int k;
    k=Convert.ToInt32(g.Returnvalue(sql));

    g.viewList("SELECT * FROM article WHERE
KeyId="+ k +" ",DataList1);
}

private void btqa_Click(object sender, System.EventArgs e)
{
    string sql="select keyid from keyword WHERE KeyWord
like '%" +txtqa.Text+"%'";
    int k;
    int YN;
    k=Convert.ToInt32(g.Returnvalue(sql));

    SqlConnection con = new
SqlConnection("server=.;database=YK5_Forum;uid=sa;");
    YN=g.Returnvalue("SELECT * FROM Question WHERE
keyid="+ k + "");
    if(YN==1)
    {
        SqlDataAdapter adp=new SqlDataAdapter("SELECT *
FROM Question WHERE keyid="+ k + "",con);
```

```

        DataSet ds=new DataSet();
        adp.Fill(ds);
        Datalist2.DataSource=ds;
        Datalist2.DataBind();
    }
    else
    {
        lblMsg.Text="Searching Item Not Found Give More
Information!";
    }
}

```

Userview.aspx

```

public int k;
private void Page_Load(object sender, System.EventArgs e)
{
    // Put user code to initialize the page here

    k=g.Returnvalue("select top 1 QuestionId from
Question order by QuestionId desc");

    if(!Page.IsPostBack)
    {
        g.viewList("Select * from Question where
QuestionId="+k+"",DataList1);
    }
    #region Web Form Designer generated code
    override protected void OnInit(EventArgs e)
    {
        //
        // CODEGEN: This call is required by the ASP.NET Web
Form Designer.
        //
        InitializeComponent();
        base.OnInit(e);
    }

    /// <summary>
    /// Required method for Designer support - do not modify
    /// the contents of this method with the code editor.
    /// </summary>
    private void InitializeComponent()
    {
        this.Button1.Click += new
System.EventHandler(this.Button1_Click);
        this.Button3.Click += new
System.EventHandler(this.Button3_Click);
        this.Button2.Click += new
System.EventHandler(this.Button2_Click);
        this.Load += new System.EventHandler(this.Page_Load);
    }
}

```

```

    }
    #endregion

    private void Button1_Click(object sender, System.EventArgs
e)
    {
        g.viewList("Select* from Question where
QuestionId="+k+" ",DataList2);
        Panell.Visible=true;
        g.viewList("Select* from Question where
QuestionId="+k+" ",DataList1);
    }

    private void Button2_Click(object sender, System.EventArgs
e)
    {
        g.insert("Update Question set
Questions='"+txtAddInformation.Text+"' where QuestionId="+k+" ");
        lblMsg.Text="Edit Successfully";
    }

    private void Button3_Click(object sender, System.EventArgs
e)
    {
        Response.Redirect("../Home/Home.aspx");
    }
}

```

Citations

1. Acharya, Kamal, *Attendance Management System Project* (April 28, 2024). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4810251> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4810251>
2. Acharya, Kamal, *Online Food Order System* (May 2, 2024). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4814732> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4814732>
3. Acharya, Kamal, *University management system project*. (May 1, 2024). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4814103> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4814103>
4. Acharya, Kamal, *Online banking management system*. (May 1, 2024). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4813597> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4813597>
5. Acharya, Kamal, *Online Job Portal Management System* (May 5, 2024). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4817534> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4817534>
6. Acharya, Kamal, *Employee leave management system*. (May 7, 2024). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4819626> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4819626>
7. Acharya, Kamal, *Online electricity billing project report*. (May 7, 2024). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4819630> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4819630>
8. Acharya, Kamal, *POLICY MANAGEMENT SYSTEM PROJECT REPORT*. (December 10, 2023). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4831694> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4831694>
9. Acharya, Kamal, *Online job placement system project report*. (January 10, 2023). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4831638> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4831638>
10. Acharya, Kamal, *Software testing for project report*. (May 16, 2023). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4831028> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4831028>
11. Acharya, Kamal, *ONLINE CRIME REPORTING SYSTEM PROJECT*. (August 10, 2022). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4831015> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4831015>
12. Acharya, Kamal, *Burger ordering system project report*. (October 10, 2022). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4832704> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4832704>

13. Acharya, Kamal, *Teachers Record Management System Project Report* (December 10, 2023). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4833821> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4833821>